

Artificial Intelligence-Based Modeling of Kerf Width and Machining Time in Cutting n-type SiC Wafer by Wire Electrical Discharge Machining

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Abstract. In the present study, an artificial intelligence (AI)-based method, namely support vector regression (SVR), was used to model kerf width and machining time in cutting n-type silicon carbide (SiC) wafer by wire electrical discharge machining (WEDM). Six process parameters, namely pulse on time, pulse off time, servo voltage, wire cutting feed rate, wire running speed, and wire tension, were considered to experimentally investigate their effects on the kerf width and machining time. A set of experimental dataset was used to build the SVR model. The variable importance of the process parameters was analyzed using the random forest method. The SVR parameters (C and ϵ) were determined by an equilibrium optimizer (EO) algorithm. The SVR-EO model proved its efficacy showing very low values of mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) and high values of absolute fraction of variation for the training and testing datasets.

Introduction

Silicon carbide (SiC) semiconductor is increasingly used in modern electronic applications such as in electric vehicles, urban transportation, sensors, radiation-resistant high-frequency and high-temperature electronic devices, smart manufacturing, radar, and communications [1,2]. However, due to their hardness and brittleness, there is a bottleneck in the fabrication of SiC devices, namely the cutting of the wafers. Cracks easily form during various processes, resulting in irregular brittle fracture. There are several methods for machining SiC, including wire electrical discharge machining (WEDM). It improves material removal rate (MRR), hardness, mechanical properties, and surface quality, and provides high precision and high efficiency of SiC [3]. In addition, it has been used to produce thinner wafers than conventional methods such as sawing with diamond wire [4]. WEDM is a non-contact process with high accuracy, in which material removal is performed by melting and evaporation. It is effective in machining difficult-to-machine materials such as hardened steel and ceramics into precise and complex geometric profiles.

The mechanism of WEDM cutting is very complicated and process-dependent, and the intricate nonlinear relationship between the parameters of the WEDM process presents a real challenge for researchers to model it with high accuracy [5]. Artificial intelligence (AI) based techniques, such as deep neural network (DNN), decision tree, naïve bayes, and support vector regression (SVR), have been extensively applied to solving and predicting results of complicated engineering problems. In many cases, these techniques obtain more accurate results than statistical methods and are highly reliable for improving the process efficiency. They can approximate any function with a high-dimensional system and are flexible in simulating nonlinear-behavior datasets [6]. DNN has been used in laser cutting of electrical steel with very high accuracy [7]. Yogesh et al. [8] used a decision tree and a naïve bayes algorithm to predict the MRR and surface roughness during WEDM cutting of aluminum composites. Paturi et al. [5] used SVR to predict the surface roughness in WEDM cutting of Inconel 718.

The aim of this work was to develop an effective SVR model for predicting kerf width and machining time in WEDM cutting of n-type SiC wafer. Six process parameters, namely pulse on time (t_{on}), pulse off time (t_{off}), servo voltage (V), wire cutting feed rate (F), wire running speed (S), and wire tension (T), were considered to experimentally investigate their effects on the kerf width and machining time. The equilibrium optimizer (EO) algorithm was used to determine the SVR parameters, namely C and ϵ .

Experimental

N-type SiC wafers with a thickness of 0.35 mm were used for the experiments. In the experiment, a straight cut of 3-mm length was performed under different combinations of process parameters. A brass wire with a diameter of 100 μm was used as the electrode. Deionized water was used as dielectric medium in all experiments. Fig. 1 shows the experimental setup.

Fig. 1 Schematic diagram of experimental setup for WEDM cutting of n-type SiC wafer.

To investigate the influence of WEDM process parameters (t_{on} , t_{off} , V , F , S , and T) on kerf width and machining time, their different levels were used (Table 1). After cutting, the kerf width was analyzed and measured using a scanning electron microscope (SEM). 32 experimental datasets were generated in this study.

Table 1 WEDM cutting process parameters used in experiment.

Parameter	Value
Pulse on time, t_{on} (μs)	5-15
Pulse off time, t_{off} (μs)	15-25
Servo voltage, V (V)	6-12
Wire cutting feed rate, F (mm/min)	3-5
Wire running speed, S (mm/s)	170-290
Wire tension, T (g)	1000-1840

SVR modeling

SVR models were used to predict kerf width and machining time using the experimental dataset generated in this study. An EO [9] was incorporated into the SVR to improve the performance of the predictive model. The EO was integrated with the SVR to generate the SVR-EO model. The EO was used to optimize the SVR parameters, namely C and ϵ . A 5-fold cross-validation (CV) was used to evaluate the quality of the SVR model when the prediction data were generated. CV is very useful when the number of datasets for training and testing is not very large or it is too difficult to provide large datasets for training [10,11]. To build the SVR-EO model, all experimental data were randomly

divided into a training set and a testing set. As described in Experimental section, 32 experimental datasets were generated in this study. In developing the SVR-EO model, 80% of the 32 datasets were used for training and the remaining 20% were used for testing. The feature matrix was used as input to the SVR model. Once the model was trained, the testing dataset were fed into the model to predict the outputs of the system. In this way, 5 SVR-EO models were generated by the 5-fold CV process. In this study, the SVR-EO prediction error was evaluated using the mean absolute percentage error (MAPE), as defined below,

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{a_i - p_i}{a_i} \right| \cdot 100\% \quad (1)$$

where a_i is the expected value, p_i is the predicted value, and n is the number of data. The SVR-EO model in this study was built using Python 3.9 (Python Software Foundation, USA) and Scikit-learn library.

Results and discussion

The percentage of variable importance of WEDM parameters associated with kerf width and machining time was calculated using a random forest method (RFM) for the experimental dataset and the results are presented in Fig. 2. The Random Forest Regressor model from the Scikit-learn library in Python 3.9 was employed. Fig. 2 shows that, among the six process parameters, t_{on} and t_{off} are the most importance factors affecting the kerf width, while paramaters V and F have a smaller contribution than t_{on} and t_{off} , but greater than that of S and T . On the other hand, parameter V had the greatest influence on machining time, as shown by the highest percentage of variable importance. The difference in the extent of variable importance between t_{on} , t_{off} , and F was not significant, but their influence on machining time was greater than that of S and T . In addition, S and T had no significant influence on kerf width and machining time.

Fig. 2 Percentage of variable importance of WEDM process parameters associated with kerf width and machining time.

The MAPEs of training and testing of 5-fold CV of the SVR-EO for the prediction of kerf width and machining time are shown in Table 2. In addition to MAPE, the performance of the SVR-EO model was also evaluated by a statistical method, namely absolute fraction of variation (R^2) [12], as follow,

$$R^2 = 1 - \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (a_i - p_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n p_i^2} \right) \quad (2)$$

The closer the R^2 value to 1 indicates a better performance of the model. The results of R^2 calculations are presented in Table 3 for the prediction of kerf width and machining time.

Table 2 MAPE of the SVR-EO models.

SVR-EO model	Kerf width MAPE (%)		Machining time MAPE (%)	
	Training	Testing	Training	Testing
1st	0.35	0.40	0.08	0.18
2nd	0.37	0.34	0.10	0.13
3rd	0.26	0.86	0.07	0.20
4th	0.33	0.50	0.10	0.02
5th	0.40	0.35	0.07	0.18

Table 3 R^2 of the SVR-EO models.

SVR-EO model	Kerf width R^2		Machining time R^2	
	Training	Testing	Training	Testing
1st	0.999961	0.999965	0.999994	0.999979
2nd	0.999966	0.999971	0.999992	0.999986
3rd	0.999973	0.999881	0.999996	0.999985
4th	0.999965	0.999956	0.999990	1.000000
5th	0.999959	0.999976	0.999995	0.999974

As shown in Table 2 and Table 3, the predictions of kerf width and machining time using the corresponding SVR model agree very well with the given experimental data as demonstrated by the low MAPE values and high R^2 values in all of the training and testing datasets. Therefore, the SVR-EO models developed in this study provide reliable models in predicting the kerf width and machining time for cutting n-type SiC wafer with WEDM.

Conclusions

This study developed effective AI-based models to predict kerf width and machining time for cutting n-type SiC wafer with WEDM using the experimental data. The following conclusions were drawn from the results of this study.

1. Quantitative analysis using the random forest method showed that pulse on time and pulse off time were the most important factors affecting kerf width. On the other hand, the servo voltage had the greatest influence on the machining time. In addition, the wire running speed and wire tension had no significant influence on kerf width and machining time.
2. The SVR-EO models developed in this study demonstrated their effectiveness with very low MAPE values and very high R^2 values for both training and testing datasets. Accordingly, the developed SVR-EO models are applicable for predicting kerf width and machining time for WEDM cutting of n-type SiC wafer.

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